

FATIGUE DEBONDING IN FIBROUS COMPOSITES

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The increased use of fibrous composites in various applications has drawn the attention to how such materials behave under fatigue loading. One possible collapse mechanism under this type of loading is progressive debonding between the fibre and the matrix. In order to investigate this mechanism, a basic model (or unit cell) was selected and the crack growth rate was measured when a time varying load was applied to the model, which consisted of an epoxy cylinder (transparent) with a steel bar in its center. It was assumed that the length of the debonded region (the crack length) at a certain moment depended in some way of the potential energy rate in analogy with Paris' crack growth law. In order to investigate this relationship the energy release rate had to be calculated, and methods for doing this is discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are used to a growing extent in all branches of industry. Especially the light, stiff and strong fibre reinforced plastics are attracting an increasing interest in these days of threatening shortage of energy. An optimal utilization of these new materials requires a thorough knowledge of their properties and the interaction between the constituents i. e. the fibres and the matrix. Debonding between fibre and matrix is a mayor type of damage in such materials. This paper deals with the problem of growing debonding between fibre and matrix in a composite subjected to a varying load. The assumption that the debonded length depends in some way on the potential energy release rate is investigated using experimental data obtained from tests performed on cylindrical transparent epoxy specimens with centrally placed steel bars.

The model used was the one shown in Fig. 1, which should be looked upon as some kind of unit cell.

Fig. 1 Model used for experimental determination of the crack growth rate. $d = 10$ mm, $D = 60$ mm and $L = 131$ mm.

In Fig. 1 the shaded part in the lower part of the specimen is held fixed.

CALCULATION OF ENERGY RELEASE RATE

Consider the surface independent integrals R_k and J_k defined by Eqs. (1) and (2) respectively.

$$R_k = \int_S \frac{1}{x_k} (W n_k - n_j \sigma_{ji} u_{i,k}) dS - \int_V \left(\frac{\sigma_{ki} u_{i,k}}{x_k^2} - \frac{W}{x_k^2} \right) dV \quad (1)$$

(k is not summed over.)

$$J_k = \int_S (W n_k - n_j \sigma_{ji} u_{i,k}) dS \quad (2)$$

In Eqs. (1) and (2) S is the boundary over which the integration is performed and V is the volume bounded by S , σ_{ij} is the stress tensor, W is the strain energy density, n_j is the outward normal to dS , u_i is the displacement vector and x_k finally is the radius vector to a point on or inside S .

R_k and J_k are derived by Broberg [1] and Knowles and Sternberg [2] respectively. Now, it is easy to show that if the stress tensor is given by $\sigma_{ij} = \partial W / \partial \epsilon_{ij}$ where ϵ_{ij} is the strain tensor and if V is free of singularities, then R_k and J_k equals zero for every $k = 1, 2, 3$. Furthermore, Budiansky and Rice [3] shows that J_k integrated over a surface enclosing a traction free crack, equals the potential energy release rate when the crack is translated in the k -direction.

In order to specialize R_k and J_k to a case of axial symmetry consider Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Integration volume.

Putting $k = 3$, i. e. considering a crack translation in the axial direction and using well known transformation formulae between stresses in Cartesian and polar co-ordinate systems one obtains

$$R_3/d\phi = J_R = \int_{\Gamma} \left(\frac{r}{z} \right) W n_z - n_j \sigma_{ij} u_{i,z} \Big|_{i,j=r,z} ds - \int_A \frac{r}{z} \left(\sigma_{rz} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial z} + \sigma_z \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} - W \right) dA \quad (z \neq 0) \quad (3)$$

$$J_3/d\phi = J_z = \int_{\Gamma} r \left(W n_z - n_j \sigma_{ij} u_{i,z} \Big|_{i,j=r,z} \right) ds \quad (4)$$

The problem to be dealt with involves the case of a crack in the interface between two different materials, see Fig. 3. It can be shown that J_R and J_z continues to be path independent also in this situation, see Gradin and Bäcklund [4]² for details.

Fig. 3 An axisymmetric crack in the interface between two different materials 1 and 2.

Assuming that a state of plane strain prevails in the vicinity of the crack tip, J_R and J_z are related to each other in a simple way. Stresses and strains near the crack tip under the above assumption will be of the form (cf Williams [5])

$$\sigma_{ij}, \epsilon_{ij} \sim \frac{1}{\sqrt{\delta}} f(\theta) \cos(\beta \ln \delta) \quad (5)$$

δ and θ are defined according to Fig. 4, β is a constant dependent of the elastic properties of both of the materials and f is some function of the angle θ .

Fig. 4 A circular integration path around the crack tip.

The integrand in the surface integral of Eq. (3) is of the type stress times strain, now using Eq. (5) and noting that $dA \sim \delta d\theta$ and letting δ tend to zero i.e. letting r and z tend to r_0 and z_0 respectively, the surface integral contribution will vanish so that

$$J_R = \frac{r_0}{z_0} \int_{\Gamma} (W n_z - n_j \sigma_{ij} u_{i,z})_{i,j=r,z} ds \quad (6)$$

J_z for the same integration path will become

$$J_z = r_0 \int_{\Gamma} (W n_z - n_j \sigma_{ij} u_{i,z})_{i,j=r,z} ds \quad (7)$$

Comparison of Eqs. (6) and (7) yields

$$J_z = z_0 J_R \quad (z_0 \neq 0) \quad (8)$$

But since J_z and J_R are both path independent Eq. (8) will hold for every path Γ surrounding the crack tip.

As was mentioned before, J_k was the potential energy release rate when the crack was translated in the k -direction. Following [3] this statement can be shown to hold also for the bimaterial case so that J_R and J_z are equivalent measures of the energy release rate.

A numerical analysis was performed on the model in Fig. 1. This analysis was carried out using the finite element program PIFEM [6] with routines for calculating J_R and J_z incorporated in it.

The finite element breakdown is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 Finite element breakdown.

$$E_{\text{steel}} = 2.07 \cdot 10^5 \text{ Mpa}; E_{\text{epoxy}} = 6.6 \cdot 10^3 \text{ Mpa}; \nu_{\text{steel}} = \nu_{\text{epoxy}} = .27$$

In Fig. 6 the relation between potential energy release rate and crack length obtained by using Eqs. (3), (4) and (8) is shown.

Fig. 6 Potential energy release rate versus crack length.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The specimens, as was mentioned in the introduction consisted of an epoxy cylinder with a polished steel bar in its center, and they were produced in the following way. In a mould according to Fig. 7 a mixture of Araldite CY219 and hardener HY977 was pored and hardened in about 70 hours in a temperature of 30°C. The inside and bottom of the mould was prepared with Silicon fat to prevent the epoxy to adhere to those parts.

Fig. 7 Schematic picture of the mould.

When the epoxy had hardened the mould was removed and the epoxy cylinder was polished, so it should be possible to measure the length of the debounded part from outside. When the specimen was inserted into the testing machine special grips were used so as to get no bending moments. The applied load was a pulsating tensile one i. e. the mean load and the load amplitude were equal.

At the beginning the crack started at some weak point and grew in some finger nail like fashion but when it had grown about 30 mm into the specimen it was almost perfectly axisymmetric.

RESULTS

In Fig. 8 the crack growth rate versus crack length for one specimen is shown, the scatter in $\frac{da}{dN}$ is probably due to both inaccuracies in measuring the crack length and to the fact that the crack is not growing perfectly uniform i. e. there are slight differences in $\frac{da}{dN}$ in different points on the crack front.

Fig. 8 Crack growth rate versus crack length.

Now with the relation between the potential energy release rate $-\frac{\partial u}{\partial a}$ and crack length a it is possible to establish the relation between $\ln \frac{da}{dN}$ and $\ln -\frac{\partial u}{\partial a}$. This is done in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9 $\ln \frac{da}{dN}$ versus $\ln -\frac{\partial u}{\partial a}$

DISCUSSION

To investigate the relation between the rate at which the debonded region between a steel bar and an epoxy cylinder grows and the release rate of potential energy, the logarithm of the crack growth rate was plotted versus the logarithm of the potential energy release rate. The result indicates a possible relation of the form $\frac{da}{dN} = C \left(-\frac{\partial U}{\partial a} \right)^m$ in analogy with Paris [7]. However, more experimental work must be performed in order to establish this relation more accurately.

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